

Optimising Microgrid Energy Management: Leveraging Flexible Storage Systems and Full Integration of Renewable Energy Sources

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Abstract

In recent years, the significance of microgrid systems has grown considerably. This research proposes an innovative approach to effectively manage uncertainty in microgrids by employing energy storage systems as the exclusive flexible resource. To address this challenge, a mathematical problem is formulated, considering two primary uncertainties associated with renewable energy sources in the microgrid: wind and photovoltaic production. The microgrid system encompasses multiple components, including a diesel generator, a micro-turbine, wind and photovoltaic power generation, an energy storage system, and the microgrid's demand. Notably, the microgrid exhibits two distinctive features: i) the complete integration of wind and photovoltaic production, and ii) the utilisation of an energy storage system as the sole flexible resource. The objective is to minimise the expected cost of the microgrid system while determining the optimal capacity of the energy storage system to meet the energy balance constraint. This constraint is crucial and takes into account the varying scenarios of wind and photovoltaic production. To illustrate the effectiveness of the proposed approach, a comprehensive case study is presented, highlighting key findings and conclusions related to the addressed problem.

Keywords: energy storage system, flexible energy source, microgrid, photovoltaic power, stochastic programming, wind power

Nomenclature

Acronyms

BESS Battery Energy Storage System

DE Diesel Generator

DER Distributed Energy Resource

EMS Energy Management System

ESS Energy Storage Systems

MG Microgrid

MILP Mixed Integer Linear Programming

MPC Predictive Control Models

MT Microturbine

NLP Non Linear Programming

OPF Optimal Power Flow

PV Photovoltaic Unit

RES Renewable Energy Source

UC Unit Commitment

V2B Vehicle-to-building

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Preprint submitted to Elsevier

January 3, 2025

W Wind Turbine

Indexes and Sets

s Index related to the scenarios from 1 to S
 t Index related to the time periods from 1 to T

Parameters

η_c Charge efficiency coefficient
 η_d Discharge efficiency coefficient
 η_{loss} Natural discharge coefficient per unit of energy [kWh]
 ρ_s Probability of occurrence of scenario s
 a_{DG} Diesel generator cost function coefficient [€/kWh²]
 a_{ESS} ESS cost function coefficient [€/kWh²]
 a_{MT} Microturbine cost function coefficient [€/kWh²]
 b_{DG} Diesel generator cost function coefficient [€/kWh]
 b_{ESS} ESS cost function coefficient [€/kWh]
 b_{MT} Microturbine cost function coefficient [€/kWh]
 b_{PV} Photovoltaic production cost coefficient [€/kWh]
 b_W Wind production cost coefficient [€/kWh]
 c_{DG} Diesel generator cost function coefficient [€]
 c_{ESS} ESS cost function coefficient [€]
 c_{MT} Microturbine cost function coefficient [€]

E_t^D Energy demand in period t [kWh]
 E_{max}^{DG} Maximum energy provided by the diesel generator [kWh]
 E_{max}^{MT} Maximum energy provided by the microturbine [kWh]
 E_{min}^{DG} Minimum energy provided by the diesel generator [kWh]
 E_{min}^{MT} Minimum energy provided by the microturbine [kWh]
 $E_{s,t}^{PV}$ PV production at scenario s and period t [kWh]
 $E_{s,t}^W$ Wind production at scenario s and period t [kWh]
 SOE_{min} Minimum state of energy [kWh]

Variables

E_t^{MT} Energy provided by the microturbine in period t [kWh]
 $C_{s,t}^{ESS}$ Cost of energy storage system at scenario s and period t [€]
 $C_{s,t}^{PV}$ Cost of photovoltaic production at scenario s and period t [€]
 $C_{s,t}^W$ Cost of wind production at scenario s and period t [€]
 C_t^{DG} Cost of diesel generator in period t [€]
 C_t^{MT} Cost of microturbine in period t [€]
 $E_{s,t}^{cESS}$ Energy charged into the energy storage system at scenario s and period t [kWh]
 $E_{s,t}^{dESS}$ Energy discharged from the energy storage system at scenario s and period t [kWh]

1. Introduction

The curtailment of renewable energy sources (RES) due to network congestion has become a stark reality. The complete integration of RES into an electric system poses a significant challenge, highlighting the importance of incorporating new flexible sources such as energy storage systems (ESS). In the context of microgrids (MG), these elements play a crucial role in achieving the power or energy balance.

Se debe traducir, e intentar unir los dos textos, el parrafo de arriba y lo que he escrito. Además se deben incorporar en los corchetes que he puesto, bibliografía actualizada.

ES NECESARIO REVISAR EL TEXTO CON LO QUE ESTÁ ESCRITO EN LA MOTIVACIÓN PARA QUE NO HAYA REPETICIÓN.

Cesar y yo nos podemos ocupar

El sector energético se encuentra inmerso en una progresiva y profunda transformación, motivada tanto por la necesidad de mitigación del cambio climático [1], como por el aprovechamiento eficiente de los recursos naturales[2]. En este sentido, el marco regulatorio y político de la UE en materia de energía insta a los estados miembros a potenciar el uso de las energías renovables y a reducir sus emisiones netas de CO₂, por medio de medidas nacionales que se materializarán a través de los denominados “Planes Integrados de Energía y Clima” [3]. Si bien el aumento de la participación de la capacidad de generación renovable constituye un vector estratégico fundamental para la descarbonización de la economía [4], el despliegue previsto para la próxima década puede provocar varios impactos en el funcionamiento del mercado y del sistema eléctrico, en el corto medio plazo[5]. Por un lado, puede producir escenarios de sobrecargas en ciertos nodos de la misma, produciendo la necesidad de incrementar sustancialmente las restricciones técnicas a las tecnologías renovables, quienes perderían parte de la energía producida [6], y por otro lado, el aumento de la participación de la generación renovable en el mix energético podría dar lugar tanto a modificaciones en la estructura del mercado como a variaciones considerables en sus precios: precio del mercado diario, precio de los servicios de ajuste, restricciones [7]. En este contexto de gran incremento y participación de la generación eléctrica renovable, adquiere especial relevancia la posibilidad de desarrollar instalaciones híbridas renovables [8]. En este panorama, las microrredes eléctricas proporcionan una solución clave para integrar recursos de energía distribuidos (DER), permiten combinar dos o más tecnologías de fuentes de energía renovables (RES) y/o sistemas de almacenamiento de energía, con recursos de energía controlables y cargas flexibles, operando en modo conectado a la red eléctrica o en modo aislado, aportando flexibilidad y resiliencia al sistema eléctrico [9]. La gestión óptima de la energía es crucial para desarrollar estrategias para mejorar la eficiencia y la confiabilidad de estos pequeños sistemas de energía eléctrica.

1.1. Motivation

The energy transition towards a decarbonised economy is one of the most significant transformations in modern society in the last decades [1]. Hence, implementing a sustainable economic model mitigating the effects of climate change becomes an obligation [2]. This energy transition started with the increased penetration of distributed energy resources (DER), mainly composed of RES. After that, new challenges appeared due to the uncertain production of RES, one of the most important being the mismatch between generation and demand. Then, ESS, Flexible Demand Management [3], and an active consumer as prosumer [4, 5] took relevance to mitigate the uncertainty introduced by the penetration of RES. Moreover, the electrification of the economic model to be sustainable is more complex due to many new actors [6]. Flexibility is a current challenge in its broadest conception [7]. Digitalisation [8] together with resilience and secure power system [9] is a new paradigm to be assumed for a sustainable economic model.

Microgrids play a fundamental role in transitioning to a sustainable economic model in which active distribution networks allow managing loads and DER. Wind (W) and photovoltaic power production (PV) require other technologies to balance the electric system. These technologies, diesel generators (DG), microturbines (MT), ESS, and flexible demand response can be connected to the distribution network or in islanded mode [10]. These technologies help the energy system’s flexibility in the current decentralisation trend of resources, providing economic, technical and environmental advantages. Flexibility is a current solution for congestion management and ancillary services [11].

1.2. Literature review

The Energy Management System (EMS) refers to a set of tools, techniques, and strategies to monitor, optimise and control the use and management of energy [12]. EMS facilitates the interaction between end-users and managers of energy resources, operators of the transmission and distribution system and the market operator.

To manage the volatility of RES, ESS technologies are considered an attractive option to provide multiple energy and power services to MG:

- Energy services (beyond pure energy arbitration): can provide load levelling, spinning reserve, temporary displacement in energy storage (time shifting), reduce or cut the peak of electrical energy demand (peak shaving) [13], [14].

- Power services: provide high response speed dynamic services that deliver synthetic inertia [15], frequency regulation [16], damping service in power oscillations [17] and stability [18].

According to the technology, ESS can be classified into mechanical, electrochemical, electrical, chemical and thermal [19]. In particular, the battery ESS (BESS) can partly provide the energy and power services raised above, although at the cost of a high level of degradation or excessive oversizing [20].

The most used mathematical models to design EMS for microgrids, which can include the optimal capacity of BESS, with RES such as solar and wind energy [21] are the optimal power flow (OPF), economic dispatch and unit commitment (UC). [22] shows that the mathematical formulation can have a single objective function to minimise the MG operation cost or multiple objective functions, maximising the reliability of the energy system. The mathematical model can also incorporate the degradation of the BESS to increase the BESS life and evaluate the size of the BESS for the MG.

Some optimisation methods and techniques are linear programming [23], mixed integer linear programming (MILP) [24, 25, 26, 27], nonlinear mixed integer programming [28], nonlinear programming (NLP) [29], dynamic programming, Stochastic Programming, artificial intelligence techniques [23], and techniques based on predictive control models (MPC) [30].

A probabilistic OPF analysis is proposed in [23], minimising the cost of installation, maintenance, and loss-of-service energy and maximising the arbitrage benefit to determine the optimal size and location of the BESS in distribution networks. [24] proposes a MILP economic dispatch for an isolated MG, minimising the total cost of the MG, considering the size of the ESS. The total cost of MG considers the investment, operation/maintenance and load shedding. The spinning reserve provided by BESS has been the subject of numerous studies to find the optimal location and size of the ESS. In [25], the authors propose a MILP model to minimise the operating costs of an isolated MG and confidence levels are established to the probability constraints of the spinning reserve. The spinning reserve restrictions have been considered in [27] and [28], considering BESS power availability to respond to contingencies in isolated MG composed of RES and conventional generation (MT and DG) due to the uncertainty caused by demand and production of RES. In [26], a UC and OPF model based on MILP is proposed for a radial network.

Other research highlights the contribution of BESS to reduce peaks (peak shaving) and smooth the demand curve. In [29], an NLP approach is proposed to control the power flow of the BESS in a distribution network with PV generation. A scheduling optimisation framework integrated into an MPC scheme is proposed in [30] for an intelligent MG EMS for a building based on PV generation and vehicle-to-building (V2B) technology. The objective of managing the exchanges of energy flows ensures the quality and continuity of the service. The results show that the proposed system contributes to reducing a 24% the peak demand in the building using the V2B concept and the energy costs for the end-user. With similar objectives to manage the peak demand (peak shaving) in an MG using BESS, a decision-tree-based algorithm is presented in [31].

1.3. Aims and contributions

The integration of ESS into MG can substantially enhance the penetration of renewable energy and promote energy-efficient utilisation. The flexibility offered by ESS plays a pivotal role in this regard. Our study emphasizes the significance of accurately sizing the ESS for an efficient energy system. This necessitates a thorough consideration of diverse factors, such as energy demand, renewable energy generation, operating expenses, and the availability of alternative energy sources. The optimal ESS size can ensure an optimised energy management strategy and enhanced system performance, ultimately contributing to a sustainable and resilient energy infrastructure. Our main contributions are:

1. The effect of the ESS on the MG to provide flexibility is evaluated for a full RES integration.
2. A new methodology to calculate the ESS capacity to provide the flexibility of the MG is introduced.
3. Compare different RES uncertainty levels that only the ESS must satisfy in and analyse its effect on the MG.

1.4. Paper organisation

The subsequent sections of this paper are structured as follows. Section 2 presents the problem description, while Section 3 outlines the mathematical model employed in our study. Section 4 introduces the case study, and Section 5 presents and discusses our findings. Finally, Section 6 illustrates the primary conclusions drawn from the results of our research.

2. Description of the problem

The MG under investigation in this study operates in isolated mode and comprises a single bus connected to various generation technologies, including a wind power plant, PV power plant, microturbine, diesel generator, and load. The MG configuration is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Microgrid energy system.

Traditionally, the uncertain power output of wind and photovoltaic generation is typically supported by a conventional generator, such as the microturbine and diesel generator [32]. However, this study exclusively addresses RES uncertainty through ESS. As a result, the MT and DG cannot offer flexibility to the MG, whereas the ESS provides the necessary flexibility to mitigate energy system uncertainty. Furthermore, the optimal ESS energy capacity must be determined to ensure total MG flexibility while minimising operational costs of the full RES integration.

3. Mathematical formulation

In the previous section, we outlined the problem associated with the MG system, which is characterised by two uncertain inputs - wind and photovoltaic power production - while other parameters, such as demand, marginal costs, and generator capacity, are considered certain. Our proposed model minimises the expected operating cost to address this problem, as illustrated in Figure 2. The model comprises four distinct constraint blocks: costs, conventional generators, energy storage system, and energy balance, all of which are essential in ensuring optimal MG performance. Consequently, the Smart FLEX-MG-EMS model generates several crucial outputs, including the total expected operating costs, ESS energy capacity, and schedules for the DG, MT, and ESS. These outputs are essential in effectively managing the MG system, optimising its performance, and minimising operating costs.

3.1. Objective function

The Smart FLEX-MG-EMS model minimises the total expected operating costs of the MG and the ESS energy capacity (1). The total expected operating costs may be split into a scenario-independent part

Figure 2: Diagram of the simulation process.

(diesel generator C_t^{DG} and microturbine cost C_t^{MT}) and a scenario-dependent part (energy storage system cost $C_{s,t}^{ESS}$ and wind and photovoltaic power production costs, $C_{s,t}^W$ and $C_{s,t}^{PV}$, respectively).

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min \sum_{t=1} (C_t^{DG} + C_t^{MT}) \\
& + \sum_{s=1} \rho_s \left(\sum_{t=1} (C_{s,t}^{ESS} + C_{s,t}^W + C_{s,t}^{PV}) \right) + SOE_{max}.
\end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

3.2. Constraints

The constraints of the Smart FLEX-MG-EMS model are organised into four distinct blocks. Each of these blocks plays a crucial role in ensuring the overall stability and efficiency of the microgrid system. These blocks are carefully designed to manage various parameters and factors, including costs, conventional generators, energy storage systems, and energy balance.

3.2.1. Cost constraints

The costs in the Smart FLEX-MG-EMS model can be classified into two types: quadratic and linear costs. The term a is associated with the quadratic term, b with the linear term and c with the constant term. Quadratic costs include the costs of the diesel generator (2), microturbine (3), and energy storage system (4), and are represented as follows:

$$C_t^{DG} = a_{DG} \cdot (E_t^{DG})^2 + b_{DG} \cdot E_t^{DG} + c_{DG}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \tag{2}$$

$$C_t^{MT} = a_{MT} \cdot (E_t^{MT})^2 + b_{MT} \cdot E_t^{MT} + c_{MT}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \tag{3}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
C_{s,t}^{ESS} &= a_{ESS} \cdot (E_{s,t}^{cESS} + E_{s,t}^{dESS})^2 \\
&+ b_{ESS} \cdot (E_{s,t}^{cESS} + E_{s,t}^{dESS}) + c_{ESS}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}.
\end{aligned} \tag{4}$$

Linear costs are employed for the wind (5) and photovoltaic (6) power plants.

$$C_{s,t}^W = b_W \cdot E_{s,t}^W; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}; \tag{5}$$

$$C_{s,t}^{PV} = b_{PV} \cdot E_{s,t}^{PV}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \tag{6}$$

Table 1: Power limits of the power plants.

Power plant	$P_{max}(kW)$	$P_{min}(kW)$
PV	40	0
W	80	0
MT	50	5
DG	100	10

3.2.2. Conventional generator constraints

The conventional generators, namely the diesel generator (7) and microturbine (8), are subject to minimum and maximum generation limits as indicated below:

$$E_{min}^{DG} \leq E_t^{DG} \leq E_{max}^{DG}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \quad (7)$$

$$E_{min}^{MT} \leq E_t^{MT} \leq E_{max}^{MT}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}. \quad (8)$$

3.2.3. Energy storage system constraints

The ESS requires maximum and minimum limits for charging (9) and discharging (10), as well as the state of energy (SOE) (11) and its limits (12). Additionally, this system incurs losses associated with the charging process η_c , discharging process η_d , and the energy stored (13).

$$0 \leq E_{s,t}^{cESS} \leq SOE_{max}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}; \quad (9)$$

$$0 \leq E_{s,t}^{dESS} \leq SOE_{max}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}; \quad (10)$$

$$SOE_{s,t} = SOE_{s,t-1} + E_{s,t}^{cESS} \cdot \eta_c - E_{s,t}^{dESS} / \eta_d - SOE_{s,t}^{loss}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}; \quad (11)$$

$$SOE_{min} \leq SOE_{s,t} \leq SOE_{max}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}; \quad (12)$$

$$SOE_{s,t}^{loss} = \eta_{loss} \cdot SOE_{s,t}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (13)$$

3.2.4. Energy balance constraint

The energy balance constraint (14) is a requirement for the MG system to balance between the amount of energy generated and the amount consumed.

$$E_t^D + E_{s,t}^{cESS} = E_t^{MT} + E_t^{DG} + E_{s,t}^W + E_{s,t}^{PV} + E_{s,t}^{dESS}; \forall t \in \mathcal{T}; \forall s \in \mathcal{S}. \quad (14)$$

4. Case study

The energy management of the MG is effectively optimised by integrating RES and an ESS, with the primary purpose of enhancing flexibility. The determination of the ESS energy capacity involves a comprehensive long-term evaluation spanning one year. The MG configuration is introduced in Section 1, and in this section, we present the input data required for the analysis.

4.1. Input data

Table 1 shows the power limits of the power plants in the MG.

The cost parameters of the power plants and ESS are shown in Table 2 [33],[34]. The costs associated with the ESS, MT, and DG power plants are represented by quadratic expressions. On the other hand, the costs related to the PV and W power plants are characterised by linear expressions.

Table 2: Cost parameters.

Power plant	a ($\text{€}/\text{kWh}^2$)	b ($\text{€}/\text{kWh}$)	c (€)
ESS	0.0001095	0.07373	0.00438
PV	-	0.0236	-
W	-	0.017	-
MT	0.000279	0.06095	0.33712
DG	0.000372	0.07214	0.64325

The charge/discharge efficiency coefficients, denoted as η_c and η_d , are set to 1. Additionally, the natural discharge coefficient per unit, represented as η_{loss} , is established as 0.05, as stated in the reference [35]. The $SOE_{t=0}$ at the beginning of the simulation is considered to be 10% of the demand, E_t^D .

We utilise 1-year hourly demand data specific to Greece for our analysis. The data is obtained from the International Energy Agency website [36] and has been appropriately scaled to achieve a maximum energy consumption of 165 kWh. Figure 3 illustrates the energy demand pattern throughout the dataset, which spans 8760 periods, with each period representing an hour. The figure visually showcases the presence of multiple peaks and off-peak periods in the yearly demand pattern, providing valuable insights into the fluctuating energy consumption over time.

Figure 3: Hourly energy demand of the microgrid.

4.2. Scenarios

In order to address the inherent uncertainty within the MG system, we incorporate scenarios as a robust modelling technique. The primary sources of uncertainty in our analysis involve the production of wind and photovoltaic sources. As our case study simulations span a lengthy timeframe, specifically a year, we employ ten scenarios to generate the key findings. This selection of scenarios allows us to comprehensively capture the range of potential outcomes, facilitating a thorough evaluation and analysis of the microgrid's performance under diverse conditions. It is important to note that these scenarios are assumed to be equiprobable, ensuring a balanced representation of the system's uncertainties.

4.2.1. Wind production scenarios

We incorporate a dataset spanning 10 years of hourly wind speed data from January 1, 2010, to December 31, 2019, specifically pertaining to Athens [37]. The data is derived from measurements taken at the standard 10-meter reference level and has been adjusted to correspond to the 40-meter level, as described in [38]. The

wind power capacity is 80 kW as shown in Table 1. To estimate the wind power production, we utilise the power curve defined by an analytical form depicted in equation (15):

$$W(t) = \begin{cases} 0 & v(t) < v_{ci}, \\ P_r \frac{v^3(t) - v_{ci}^3}{v_r^3 - v_{ci}^3} & v_{ci} < v(t) < v_r, \forall t \in \{1, 2, \dots, 24\}. \\ P_r & v_r < v(t) < v_{co}, \\ 0 & v(t) > v_{co}, \end{cases} \quad (15)$$

where P_r and v_r are the rated power (kW) and the wind speed (m/s), respectively. v_{ci} , v_{co} and $v(t)$ are the cut-in, cut-out and actual wind speeds, respectively.

Wind energy production is modeled as a non-homogeneous Markov reward process as done in [27], where a random variable J_n^W is considered with values in the state set $E^W = \{1, 2, 3, 4, 5\}$. The five states in the set denote the system's different levels of generated wind power. State 1 corresponds to the energy values between 0 and 16 kW, state 2 to the power values between 16 and 32 kW, state 3 to the power values between 32 and 48 kW, state 4 to the power values between 48 and 64 kW, and state 5 to power values between 64 and 80 kW. J_n^W indicates the state of the system at the transition $n - th$. The transition from one hour to the next is governed by a probability transition matrix that depends on the time of day. We have 24 probability transition matrices that depend on the time of the day and satisfy the relationship (16).

$$\begin{aligned} & P[J_{n+1}^W = j \mid J_n^W = i_n, J_{n-1}^W = i_{n-1}, \dots, J_1^W \\ & = i_1, J_0^W = i_0] \\ & = P[J_{n+1}^W = j \mid J_n^W = i_n] = p_{i_n j}(n+1). \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

We can compute the multi-step transition probability function by using the formula (17):

$$\prod_{k=t'+1}^t P^W(k); t', t \in \mathbb{N}; 0 \leq t' \leq t. \quad (17)$$

The generic (i, j) -element of the product matrix denotes the probability of having a wind power equal to j at time t , given that at time t' the wind power generated was equal to i .

Once the non-homogeneous Markov chain has been derived, each state assigns a random reward corresponding to a specific wind power production falling within the intervals associated with the state of E^W . This is achieved by randomly selecting a value from the dataset of wind power measurements that falls within the relevant state.

4.2.2. Photovoltaic production

We utilise a dataset consisting of hourly solar irradiation data over a period of 10 years, ranging from January 1, 2010, to December 31, 2019, focusing on the region of Athens [37]. To estimate the photovoltaic power production, we employ the equation proposed in references [39], which PV power capacity is 40 kW as shown in Table 1:

$$PV(t) = P_{STC} \frac{n \cdot E_M(t)}{E_{STC}} [1 + h(T_M(t) - T_{STC})], \quad \forall t \in \{1, 2, \dots, 24\}. \quad (18)$$

where $PV(t)$ is the output power of the photovoltaic plant at time t , $E_M(t)$ and $T_M(t)$ are the solar irradiance at time t and the module temperature at time t , respectively. In particular, the latter depends on the ambient temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$) and the constant module provided by the producer [39], and can be calculated as $T_M(t) = T_{amb} + \varepsilon_{PV} \frac{E_M(t)}{E_{STC}}$. P_{STC} , E_{STC} and T_{STC} are the maximum power, the irradiance,

and the temperature under Standard Test Conditions (STC), respectively. These values are obtained by a temperature of the cell equal to 25 °C and an irradiance equal to 1000 W/m² with air mass 1.5. n indicates the number of PV panels, h the power temperature coefficient (%/°C), and ε_{PV} is a constant module provided by the manufacturer.

We employ a detrending technique to remove any long-term trends in the photovoltaic power data. Specifically, we compute the average hourly power for each month throughout the year and calculate the difference between this average and the corresponding photovoltaic power data. By doing so, we obtain residuals that capture the short-term fluctuations. As done in [27], these residuals are then modelled using a homogeneous Markov reward process, as detailed in [40].

A random variable J_n^{PV} with values in set $E^{PV} = \{1, 2, 3\}$ is considered. E^{PV} contains three states because the residuals are divided into positive, negative, or equal to 0. J_n^{PV} indicates the state of the system at the n -th transition. The transition matrix must satisfy the following relation (19):

$$\begin{aligned} P[J_{n+1}^{PV} = j \mid J_n^{PV} = i_n, J_{n-1}^{PV} = i_{n-1}, \dots, J_1^{PV} = i_1, \\ J_0^{PV} = i_0] = P[J_{n+1}^{PV} = j \mid J_n^{PV} = i_n] = p_{ij}. \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

The transition probabilities of the Markov chain that represents the photovoltaic production are independent of time n and, consequently, the process is homogeneous over time. After obtaining the simulated residual Markov chain, a random reward is assigned to each state within the chain. This is accomplished by selecting a value from the set of values associated with the corresponding state. Subsequently, the detrended power is added to the simulated residuals.

Figure 4 presents the hourly average wind and PV energy production. An interesting observation can be made by comparing this figure with Figure 3. It is evident that during periods of high energy demand, the wind and PV power plants exhibit lower production levels. Conversely, wind production reaches its maximum capacity throughout the remainder of the year, while PV production displays considerable variability. This analysis sheds light on the inverse relationship between energy demand and renewable energy generation, highlighting the need for effective strategies to balance supply and demand in the microgrid system.

Figure 4: Hourly average wind and PV production.

5. Results and discussion

Initially, we assess the stability of the objective function and the energy capacity of the ESS solution by varying the number of scenarios. This evaluation is crucial since our analysis focuses on long-term

considerations spanning a duration of one year. Figures 5 and 6 demonstrate the stability of the results across different scenarios. Specifically, we observe that employing 10 scenarios ensures consistent outcomes, prompting us to select this number for further MG analysis.

Figure 5: Objective function and maximum energy capacity of the ESS regarding the number of scenarios.

Figure 6: Maximum energy capacity of the ESS and CPU time regarding the number of scenarios.

The mathematical model successfully identifies an optimal solution for the MG, yielding a minimum expected cost of 97721.58 € and 1494.91 kWh considering ten scenarios. Correspondingly, Figures 5 and 6 illustrate the evolution of the objective function, maximum energy capacity of the ESS and CPU time regarding the number of scenarios. These figures provide visual confirmation of the model’s decision-making process and further reinforce the chosen parameters’ efficacy in achieving the microgrid’s cost-efficient operation.

The model is programmed in Python [41] and Pyomo [42] which solver is Gurobi [43] in a 11th Gen Intel(R) Core(TM) i5 at 2.40GHz, 4 physical cores, using up to 8 threads and 8 GB of RAM. The CPU time of the 10 scenarios is 73 min.

5.1. Results and discussion

The results presented in this section are for ten scenarios. The DG and MT production are presented in Figure 7 together with the Demand. As we can see, the DG production follows the demand pattern while the MT production tries to produce the maximum energy, reducing some periods where the DG production is increased regarding the previous period. The remaining energy to satisfy the demand comes from the wind, PV and ESS production.

Figure 7: DG and MT production, and energy demand.

Figure 8 depicts the hourly average profile of the ESS, showcasing the charging and discharging activities as well as the SOE. This profile represents the average behaviour observed across the ten scenarios considered. Notably, the Figure 8 illustrates instances where the ESS simultaneously charges and discharges, reflecting the diverse scenarios where some scenarios require charging while others necessitate discharging. Furthermore, the ESS profile exhibits characteristics influenced by both wind and PV production, indicating the dynamic interplay between renewable energy sources and the storage system. It is worth mentioning that the maximum energy capacity of the ESS, as determined by the ten scenarios, is 1494.91 kWh, while the maximum hourly average SOE reaches 818.06 kWh. The disparity between the two values arises from the volatility inherent in the scenarios, with the maximum energy capacity designed to accommodate worst-case scenarios characterized by heightened volatility. It should be noted that if the energy capacity of the ESS falls below 1494.91 kWh, the optimisation problem becomes infeasible.

Figure 8: Hourly average ESS charge/discharge and average SOE.

To gain a deeper understanding of the relationship between the maximum energy capacity of the ESS and renewable generation, we examine the average standard deviation alongside the maximum ESS energy capacity. Figure 9 presents this analysis, illustrating the maximum ESS energy capacity and the standard deviation of wind and PV production for different numbers of scenarios. Notably, the volatility pattern exhibits a resemblance to a logarithmic function, mirroring the trend observed in Figure 5. It is worth highlighting that for the ten scenarios considered, the solution tends to approach the asymptotes of the logarithmic curve, ultimately converging towards a maximum energy capacity of approximately 1500 kWh.

Table 3: MG total costs (€), maximum ESS energy capacity (kWh) and Avg. standard deviation ($\bar{\sigma}_{RES}$) of RES (kWh).

N ^o Sce.	MG total cost	ESS Max. Cap.	$\bar{\sigma}_{RES}$
1	65001.67	161.09	0
2	83691.16	1350.86	17.06
3	89110.98	1363.07	21.71
4	92040.14	1488.54	24.15
5	93931.27	1488.54	25.15
6	95419.49	1488.54	26.23
7	96116.70	1488.54	26.76
8	96629.77	1488.54	27.17
9	97068.93	1494.92	27.56
10	97721.58	1494.92	27.89

This discovery indicates that utilising ten scenarios provides a near-optimal solution that effectively aligns with the capacity requirements of the MG system.

Figure 9: Maximum energy capacity of the ESS vs standard deviation of the renewable sources.

The complete integration of unpredictable RES such as wind and PV production within a MG, relying solely on an ESS, results in a significant increase in the required ESS energy capacity. By enabling the full utilisation of 100% of the wind and PV production without any curtailment, the energy capacity of the ESS experiences a substantial expansion. As evident from the preceding findings, the ESS energy capacity reaches nearly ten times the peak energy demand of the system. This observation underscores the necessity of a sufficiently large ESS capacity to accommodate the intermittent nature of RES and ensure the reliable operation of the MG system.

Table 3 presents the expected operating costs of the MG, the corresponding ESS maximum energy capacity, and the average standard deviation of the RES within the MG. Notably, the minimum cost is achieved when there is no uncertainty, represented by a single scenario, while the maximum cost is associated with ten scenarios exhibiting the highest volatility. It is noteworthy that the operational cost of the MG shows a more significant increase with the volatility of the RES compared to a higher ESS energy capacity. This finding highlights the importance of effectively managing and mitigating the volatility of RES to minimise the operational costs of the MG system.

6. Conclusions

In this study, a mathematical model was proposed to minimise the operational cost of a MG while optimising the ESS maximum energy capacity. An essential aspect of the mathematical model is the complete integration of RES in the isolated microgrid, with the ESS serving as the sole flexible resource. Based on the simulations and analysis conducted, the following key conclusions can be drawn:

- Higher volatility in RES generation results in increased operational costs and necessitates a larger ESS energy capacity.
- Utilising a single flexible resource like the ESS leads to significantly higher energy capacity requirements for the ESS.
- Avoiding curtailment of RES generation leads to a higher ESS energy capacity requirement.

These findings emphasize the importance of effectively managing RES volatility, optimising flexible resource utilisation, and minimising curtailment to achieve cost-efficient and sustainable MG operation. Further research and exploration in these areas can contribute to the development of more robust and efficient MG systems.

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